

RESEARCH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOFT MEDICINES

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Relevance: Ibuprofen is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug from the group of propionic acid derivatives, which has an analgesic and antipyretic effects. Ibuprofen is most popular in the treatment of rheumatic pain in order to stop joint syndrome. The mechanism of analgesic action of the drug is due to a decrease in prostaglandin production. In order to avoid the side effects of Ibuprofen when administered orally, we developed a gel of the liposomal form of Ibuprofen.

Research objective: The aim of the study was to study the acute toxicity and irritant effect of the liposomal form of Ibuprofen in order to determine its safety when applied topically.

Materials and methods: Acute toxicity of the liposomal form of Ibuprofen was studied in outbred white male rats weighing 140-150 g. Studies were conducted on 4 groups of animals, 6 animals in each group, a total of 18 animals. Liposomal gel form of Ibuprofen nanhave mastered gradually, once on a clipped area of the skin of the back and sides of rats measuring 30 cm² (4 x 7.5 cm) in a dose of 2.5 mg / kg, 5 Animals were placed in separate cages, the skin area with the test substance was left open, observation was carried out hourly on the day of administration, 3 times a day for 2-3 days and once a day for the next 14 days of the experiment. General behavior, skin condition, redness, coat condition, and motor activity were taken into account. The back temperature was determined in degrees Celsius (C°) in the skin fold with an electronic thermometer before applying the test solution and after applying after 6 and 12 hours. Toxicity was determined by the presence of rat mortality.

Calculation of acute toxicity indicators due to the absence of dead rats turned out to be impossible, which indicates a low toxicity of the drug.

To determine the irritant effect of the drug, sexually mature albino rabbits weighing at least 2 kg were used, the study was conducted on 3 animals weighing 2.2, 2.5, 2.7 kg. A day before the study, the rabbit's hair was cut in areas of 10 x 15 cm on both sides of the back for application and observation. Application of the test material and control was performed on both sides of the rabbit's back. Areas with the applied material on top were covered with pieces of cloth or gauze, folded in four, with an area of 25 x 25 mm and fixed with a bandage. The exposure time was at least 4 hours. The protective bandage and pieces of cloth were removed, and the position of the areas was noted. Then, the remaining test substance was removed with 0.9% sodium chloride solution.

When exposed, the condition of each skin area where applications were performed was recorded 1, 24, 48, and 72 hours after removal of the samples. The degree of skin reaction, including erythema and edema, was described and evaluated according to the classification provided in the appendix for each site and each observation time interval.

Research results. The results of the acute toxicity study indicate that the drug in the studied doses does not affect the behavior pattern and general condition of animals. In all periods of the study, the skin of the back of rats did not significantly differ from the initial state. No

deaths of animals under the influence of the studied doses of the drug are observed. The drug in the studied doses also does not have a skin-irritating effect.

Conclusions: The liposomal form of Ibuprofen gel is a low-toxic agent and does not have a skin-irritating effect.